

K-Corruption Intermittent Attacks for Violating the Codiagnosability

Ruotian Liu, *Member, IEEE*, Yihui Hu, Agostino Marcello Mangini, *Senior Member, IEEE*, and Maria Pia Fanti, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—In this work, we address the codiagnosability analysis problem of a networked discrete event system under malicious attacks. The considered system is modeled by a labeled Petri net and is monitored by a series of sites, in which each site possesses its own set of sensors, without requiring communication among sites or to any coordinators. A net is said to be codiagnosable with respect to a fault if at least one site could deduce the occurrence of this fault within finite steps. In this context, we focus on a type of malicious attack that is called stealthy intermittent replacement attack. The stealthiness demands that the corrupted observations should be consistent with the system’s normal behavior, while the intermittent replacement setting entails that the replaced transition labels must be recovered within a bounded of consecutive corrupted observations (called as K -corruption intermittent attack). Particularly, there exists a coordination between attackers that are separately effected on different sites, which holds the same corrupted observation for each common transition under attacks. From an attacker viewpoint, this work aims to design K -corruption intermittent attacks for violating the codiagnosability of systems. For this purpose, we propose an attack automaton to analyze K -corruption intermittent attack for each site, and build a new structure called complete attack graph that is used to analyze all the potential attacked paths. Finally, an algorithm is inferred to obtain the K -corruption intermittent attacks, and examples are given to show the proposed attack strategy.

Index Terms—Discrete event system, decentralized structure, Petri net, intermittent attack, codiagnosability.

NOMENCLATURE

N	Petri net.
M_0	Initial marking of a Petri net.
\mathcal{N}	Labeled Petri net (LPN).
T_u	Set of unobservable transitions.
T_o	Set of observable transitions.
T_f	Set of fault transitions.
T_{reg}	Set of regular unobservable transitions.
$T_{r,a}$	Set of regular unobservable transitions that can be attacked.

This work was supported in part by the IN2CCAM project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101076791, and the Natural Science Basic Research Program of Shaanxi Province under Grant 2024JC-YBQN-0669. This manuscript reflects only the authors’ views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them. (Corresponding author: Ruotian Liu.)

Ruotian Liu, Agostino Marcello Mangini, and Maria Pia Fanti are with the Department of Electrical and Information Engineering, Polytechnic University of Bari, 70125 Bari, Italy (e-mails: {ruotian.liu, agostinomarcello.mangini, mariapia.fanti}@poliba.it).

Yihui Hu is with the School of Automation, Xi’an University of Posts and Telecommunications, 710121 Xi’an, China (e-mail: huyihui@xupt.edu.cn).

$T_{r,u}$	Set of regular unobservable transitions that cannot be attacked.
$\pi(\sigma)$	Parikh vector of σ .
l	Labeling function.
l^j	Labeling function of site j .
Σ	Event set.
Σ^j	Event set of site j .
$P_{r,u}(\sigma)$	Projection of σ over $T_{r,u}$.
G_e	Extended basis reachability graph (EBRG).
\mathcal{J}	Set of sites in LPN system.
M_d	Dead marking.
G_ε	ε -BRG: enhanced version of EBRG.
$G_{\varepsilon,n}^j$	Nonfailure ε -BRG of site j .
U_ε	ε -unfolded verifier.
\mathcal{A}	Attack structure.
\mathcal{A}^j	Attack structure of site j .
$\Sigma_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t)$	Set of replaced labels associated with t in terms of \mathcal{A}^j .
$T_{a,s}^j$	Attackable transitions with respect to \mathcal{A}^j .
l_a^j	Modified labeling function of site j .
A^j	Replacement attack of site j .
A	Attack tuple.
K^j	Maximum value of consecutive corrupted observation of site j .
K	Row vector whose j -th element is K^j .
T_a^j	Set of attackable transitions that are associated with different labels with respect to site j .
T_{na}^j	Set of attackable transitions that hold their original labels with respect to site j .
I_j	Insertion function of site j .
I_j^{-1}	Inverse of insertion function.
$\tilde{P}_{a,na}^j$	Projection over $T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j$.
$P_{a,na}^{f,j}$	Projection over $T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j \cup T_f$.
Φ_j	K -corruption intermittent attack function of site j .
Δ_j	Attack automaton of site j .
U_c	Complete attack graph.
$\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j$	Projection over $T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j$ of site j .
$\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f$	Projection over $T \cup T_a \cup T_{na}$.
$l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t)$	Set of observations when t fires with respect to \mathcal{A}^j .

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber physical systems (CPSs) integrate sensing, control and networking into physical processes, in which network communication makes the system vulnerable to various network attacks, such as sensor reading corruption and actuator command alteration [1]–[4]. Such attack scenarios of CPSs

have attracted much attention in the community of discrete event systems (DESs): mainly concerning the problems of attack detection [5]–[7], attack synthesis [8]–[13], state estimation [14], [15]. This work focuses on the attack synthesis problem for violating the codiagnosability in DESs.

Diagnosability is a system property determining whether the occurrence of a fault can be detected within finite steps, and has been studied in the framework of automata [16]–[18] and Petri nets [19]–[24]. In practice, many large complex systems are monitored by a set of sites that consider variable communication delays and errors when transmitting diagnostic information from different sites to a coordinator. It is impossible or very costly to collect all data at a central station. Thus, the information structure of the system is naturally considered to be decentralized, and in practice, there exist two main aspects for the decentralized setting. One is about the notion of decentralized diagnosis involving communication among sites, such as [25]–[27]. The other is the concept of decentralized diagnosis, which does not involve communication among sites. The notion of *codiagnosability* requires that the occurrence of any fault can be detected by at least one site using its own observations of the system execution within a bounded delay [28]–[31]. To investigate the codiagnosability of the system, this work considers the Protocol 3 in [32] that does not require any coordination between sites.

The idea of this work is inspired by recent studies [29], [33] that deal with the codiagnosability analysis or opacity enforcement problem by relabeling transitions or inserting transition labels when no active attack exists. Meanwhile, some studies [34], [35] tackle the problem of robust codiagnosability against sensor failures, guaranteeing the safety and reliability of the systems. Here, we investigate the contrary aspects to codiagnosability enforcement [29] and robust codiagnosability [34]–[36] from an attacker viewpoint. It is motivated by the necessity of design with an attack policy for violating the codiagnosability, which conceals the occurrence of critical faults to compromise the systems. For instance, an intruder attempts to disrupt the bank security system by manipulating the sensor readings in the network communication components. This manipulation is intended to evade the system’s ability to detect faults or trigger alerts, thus rendering the system non-diagnosable under such an attack. As we know, other works investigating the attack synthesis problem focus on different attack objectives. For example, the violation of safety, i.e., all internal strings generated by the system are legal, is considered in [8], [12], while the violation of opacity is studied in [13].

In the aforementioned attack studies, the system observation may be corrupted by the attackers continuously to compromise the system, where the problem of intermittent corruption is not considered in DESs. In fact, intermittent attacks [37] require lower energy cost compared to continuous attacks. On the other hand, attackers exploit intermittent vulnerabilities of the systems, like camera downtime during security personnel shifts or maintenance periods. These intermittent vulnerabilities result in disruptions in the digital trail, making detection more challenging. In this work, we formulate intermittent attack synthesis problem in DESs under the decentralized framework, where the considered attack could last for at most

a certain period of time. To do so, we assume that after a bounded number of consecutive corrupted observations under the intermittent attacks, the replaced transition label must be recovered, which leads to a new notion of *K-corruption intermittent attack*. Particularly, in a decentralized structure, given a transition sequence and a site j , if the transitions have been replaced a given certain K^j times consecutively under the attacks, then the next occurrence of a transition that can be attacked should hold its original label.

Note that our intermittent setting is inspired by the work [35] that focuses on the robust codiagnosability verification against intermittent or transient sensor failures. However, two main differences exist between our study and the work [35]: i) in terms of problem formulation and solution, we aim to synthesize an intermittent attack strategy for violating the codiagnosability, while paper [35] investigates the problem of robust codiagnosability verification, thus yielding to different solutions; ii) in terms of formalism, the proposed problem is newly addressed in the labeled Petri net (LPN) formalism, where the techniques of basis marking and linear algebra are used to avoid an exhaustive computation of all markings. In addition, work [36] proposes a uniform approach for diagnosis in DESs subject to unreliable sensors, employing linear temporal logic techniques. Such a framework allows for the formulation and inclusion of diagnosability verification problems in terms of K -loss observation setting, but it is not applied for the enforcement or violation of diagnosability. It is noteworthy that the considered attack scenario may compromise observations by inserting, replacing, or removing partial observations within the system. Sensor failure typically results in incorrect or missing observations. Our work complements existing research on attack synthesis problems in DESs, with a particular emphasis on addressing intermittent attacks. By devising such an attack strategy, our aim is to enable engineers to detect potential vulnerabilities from the perspective of an attacker.

To tackle the attack synthesis problem, there are mainly several approaches in the literature. The first type of approaches [12], [13] employs a discrete structure to model the game-like interaction between the supervisor and the attacker. Such a game structure incorporates all possible attacks. The second type of approaches transforms the attack synthesis problem into the supervisor synthesis problem [8], [9]. Unlike existing approaches, we introduce a labeling function to model an attack, for making a system non-codiagnosable by using an ε -unfolded verifier structure. Specifically, an attack synthesis requires the existence of a type of path called elementary unsound path that violates the codiagnosability. The classic verifier [29] can only update states when consecutive transition pairs have the same observation, thus it is unable to generate elementary unsound paths. In addition, the classic verifier cannot be applied to intermittent attack synthesis. To solve these issues, we develop a new structure called complete attack graph with the following advantages: (i) it removes the same observation condition of the consecutive transition pair; (ii) it integrates the proposed attack automaton, such that all the potential attacked paths limited to K consecutive corruptions are listed. Moreover, unlike the approach in [12],

which achieves stealthiness through state pruning, this study identifies stealthy attacks by analyzing the corrupted behavior.

Later on, to apply the concept of codiagnosability without deadlock-freeness assumption, we add a self-loop labeled with the empty string ε to each determined dead marking. The origin of this concept is derived from the research [31] where a verifier structure is proposed to determine the diagnosability of a system with deadlocks. However, unlike the work in [31], this study primarily focuses on the design of an attack strategy violating the codiagnosability. The main contribution of this paper is summarized as follows:

- We first formulate the K -corruption intermittent attack synthesis problem of a system modeled by LPN in the decentralized framework. To our knowledge, this issue has not been previously considered in DESs.
- We develop a new structure called a complete attack graph that contains all the attacked paths limited to K consecutive corruptions, based on the notion of extended basis marking and attack automaton. Then some conditions are given to determine the potential attacked path that could be attacked into a predefined elementary unsound path leading to the violation of codiagnosability.
- We propose an algorithm to obtain K -corruption intermittent attacks for violating the codiagnosability. Particularly, a coordination between attackers separately effected on different sites holds the same corrupted observation for each common transition. Moreover, we guarantee the stealthiness of attacks, i.e., its occurrence cannot be distinguished from the system behavior. To this aim, it is required that the set of corrupted observations is contained in the set of observations without attacks.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows. Section II presents basic definitions of LPNs as well as the notion of extended basis reachability graph. In Section III, we propose an extended unfolded verifier for codiagnosability analysis, and then define the stealthy replacement and intermittent (in terms of K consecutive corrupted observations) attack. The addressed codiagnosability analysis problem is formulated in the LPNs under the K -intermittent attack. Section IV proposes an approach to obtain attacks for violating the codiagnosability. Finally, conclusions are summarized in Section V.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Petri net

Let \mathbb{N} be the set of non-negative integers. A Petri net is defined as a four-tuple $N = (P, T, Pre, Post)$, where $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ is a set of $m \in \mathbb{N}$ places, $T = \{t_1, \dots, t_n\}$ is a set of $n \in \mathbb{N}$ transitions with $P \cup T \neq \emptyset$ and $P \cap T = \emptyset$, $Pre : P \times T \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ and $Post : P \times T \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ are the *pre-* and *post-incidence* matrices, respectively, denoting the weights of the arcs from places to transitions and transitions to places, which fix the structure of a net and are represented as matrices in $\mathbb{N}^{m \times n}$. The incidence matrix of a net is defined by $C = Post - Pre$. A Petri net is said to be *acyclic* if there is no directed cycle.

A marking is a mapping $M : P \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ that assigns to a place of a Petri net a non-negative integer of tokens, graphically

denoted by black dots. $M(p_i)$ is the number of tokens in place p_i at a marking M . A Petri net system $\langle N, M_0 \rangle$ is a net N with an initial marking M_0 . A transition $t \in T$ is enabled at a marking M if $M \geq Pre(\cdot, t)$ and may fire yielding a marking $M' = M + C(\cdot, t)$. We write $M[\sigma]$ to denote that a transition sequence $\sigma = t_1 t_2 \dots t_i \in T^*$ is enabled at M , and $M[\sigma]M'$ to denote that the firing of σ yields M' . When σ and σ' are two sequences, $\sigma\sigma'$ stands for the concatenation of σ and σ' . The Parikh vector of σ is denoted by $\pi(\sigma)$ and maps a transition $t \in T$ to the number of occurrences of t in σ . The cardinality of the set (\cdot) is denoted by $|\cdot|$.

A marking M is reachable in $\langle N, M_0 \rangle$ if there exists a firing sequence $\sigma \in T^*$ such that $M_0[\sigma]M$. The set of all markings reachable from M_0 , denoted by $R(N, M_0)$, defines the reachability set of $\langle N, M_0 \rangle$, i.e., $R(N, M_0) = \{M \in \mathbb{N}^m \mid M_0[\sigma]M\}$. The set of transition sequences enabled at the initial marking M_0 is defined as $L(N, M_0) = \{\sigma \in T^* \mid M_0[\sigma]\}$. Given a transition sequence set $H \subseteq L(N, M_0)$, we denote by H/σ the post transition sequence of a sequence $\sigma \in H$, i.e., $H/\sigma = \{\sigma' \in L(N, M_0) \mid \sigma\sigma' \in H\}$. A marking M is *dead* if there is no any transition enabled at M . A net system $\langle N, M_0 \rangle$ is said to be: *bounded* if there exists an integer $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $M \in R(N, M_0)$ and for all $p_i \in P, M(p_i) \leq k$ holds; *deadlock-free* if for all $M \in R(N, M_0)$, M is not dead.

Given a Petri net $N = (P, T, Pre, Post)$ and a subset of transitions $T' \subseteq T$, the T' -induced subnet of N is a Petri net $N' = (P, T', Pre', Post')$, where Pre' and $Post'$ are the restrictions of Pre and $Post$ to $P \times T'$, respectively, i.e., the net N' is obtained by removing all the transitions in $T \setminus T'$ from N .

B. Labeled Petri net

Given a Petri net $N = (P, T, Pre, Post)$ and an event set Σ , a labeling function $l : T \rightarrow \Sigma \cup \{\varepsilon\} = \Sigma_\varepsilon$ assigns to a transition either a symbol from the event set Σ or the empty string symbol ε . A labeled Petri net (LPN) system $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ is a Petri net system $\langle N, M_0 \rangle$ with a labeling function l and an event set Σ . A transition t is said to be unobservable or silent if it is associated with the empty string ε , i.e., $l(t) = \varepsilon$. The set of unobservable transitions is denoted by $T_u = \{t \in T \mid l(t) = \varepsilon\}$. The other transitions labeled with events from Σ are called observable transitions, denoted as $T_o = \{t \in T \mid l(t) \in \Sigma\}$. Hence, the set of transitions T can be divided into two disjoint sets T_o and T_u with $T = T_o \cup T_u$. Furthermore, the set T_u can be divided into two disjoint sets T_f and T_{reg} with $T_u = T_f \cup T_{reg}$, where T_f and T_{reg} denote the sets of fault transitions and regular unobservable transitions, respectively. The set T_f can be further partitioned into r classes T_f^i , where $i = 1, \dots, r$. For simplicity, this work considers an LPN with a single fault class, i.e., $T_f = T_f^1$. Nevertheless, the proposed approach could be easily extended to the nets with multiple fault classes as presented in [29]. In addition, from a practical point of view, we partition the set T_{reg} into two disjoint sets $T_{r,a}$ and $T_{r,u}$ with $T_{reg} = T_{r,a} \cup T_{r,u}$, where $T_{r,a}$ (resp., $T_{r,u}$) denotes the set of regular unobservable transitions that can (resp. cannot) be attacked.

The labeling function could be extended to a transition sequence $\sigma = t_1 t_2 \dots t_i$ such that $\omega = l(\sigma) = l(t_1)l(t_2) \dots l(t_i)$, which is called an *observation* corresponding to the sequence σ . Given an LPN system $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$, we define $l^{-1}(\omega)$ as the set of all transition sequences consistent with $\omega \in \Sigma_\varepsilon^*$, i.e., $l^{-1}(\omega) = \{\sigma \in L(N, M_0) \mid l(\sigma) = \omega\}$. Note that the observation $\omega = \varepsilon \cdot \varepsilon^h = \varepsilon$, $h \in \mathbb{N}$. The language generated by an LPN system S is defined as $\mathcal{L}(N, M_0) = \{\omega \in \Sigma_\varepsilon^* \mid \exists \sigma \in L(N, M_0) : \omega = l(\sigma)\}$, i.e., the language $\mathcal{L}(N, M_0)$ is a set of observations corresponding to the transition sequences in $L(N, M_0)$.

C. Extended basis reachability graph

In this subsection, we recall necessary notions of the extended basis markings in [38]. Give a transition sequence $\sigma \in T^*$, we denote by $P_{r,u}(\sigma)$ the projection of σ over $T_{r,u}$. Moreover, the restriction of incidence matrix C of an LPN system to $T_{r,u}$ is denoted by $C_{r,u}$.

Definition 2.1 ([38]): Given a marking $M \in R(N, M_0)$ and a transition $t \in T_o \cup T_f \cup T_{r,a}$ of an LPN system $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$, the set of explanations of t at M is defined by $\Sigma(M, t) = \{\sigma \in T_{r,u}^* \mid M[\sigma]M', M'[t]\}$, and the set of explanation vectors of t at M is denoted as $Y(M, t) = \{\pi(\sigma) \in \mathbb{N}^{|T_{r,u}|} \mid \sigma \in \Sigma(M, t)\}$. In addition, the minimal explanation vector is defined as $Y_{\min}(M, t) = \{\pi(\sigma) \in Y(M, t) \mid \nexists \pi(\sigma') \in Y(M, t) : \pi(\sigma') \preceq \pi(\sigma)\}$. \diamond

The set of *extended basis markings*, denoted as X_e , is recursively computed as follows:

- $M_0 \in X_e$;
- If $M \in X_e$, then for each $t \in T_o \cup T_{r,a} \cup T_f$, $y = \pi(\sigma) \in Y_{\min}(M, t)$, $(M' = M + C_{r,u} \cdot y + C(\cdot, t)) \Rightarrow (M' \in X_e)$.

Given an LPN system $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$, the *extended basis reachability graph* (EBRG) of S is a nondeterministic finite state automaton $G_e = (X_e, E, \delta, M_0)$, where X_e is the set of states (i.e., extended basis markings); $E \subseteq (T_o \times \Sigma) \cup [(T_f \cup T_{r,a}) \times \varepsilon]$ is the set of event labels; $\delta \subseteq X_e \times \Sigma_\varepsilon \times X_e$ is the transition relation; and M_0 is the initial state. In particular, the transition relation $(M, e, M') \in \delta$ where $e = t(l(t)) \in T_o \times \Sigma$ or $e = t(\varepsilon) \in (T_f \cup T_{r,a}) \times \varepsilon$ if and only if $\exists y \in Y_{\min}(M, t), M' = M + C_{r,u} \cdot y + C(\cdot, t)$.

III. CODIAGNOSABILITY ANALYSIS PROBLEM UNDER MALICIOUS ATTACKS

In this work, we consider that the system is monitored by a set of sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$ associated with their own observable event sets, where ξ is equal to the number of sites. Each transition in T_o is assumed to be observable by at least one site, i.e., $T_o = \bigcup_{j \in \mathcal{J}} T_o^j$, where $T_o^j \subseteq T_o$ is the set of transitions that are observable by site j . The event set of site j is $\Sigma^j \subseteq \Sigma$, and

$$l^j(t) = \begin{cases} l(t) & \text{if } l(t) \in \Sigma^j, \\ \varepsilon & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

denotes the labeling function of site j .

A. Codiagnosability analysis based on ε -unfolded verifier

The codiagnosability analysis approach proposed in [29] relies on the assumption that the net system is deadlock-free when using the unfolded verifier. Nevertheless, this work eliminates the assumption by introducing a self-loop encoded with an additional unobservable transition t_u (labeled by the empty string ε and cannot be attacked) to each dead marking. Consequently, the resulting transition sequence set could be defined as $L^\omega(N, M_0) = L(N, M_0) \cup \{\sigma t_u^* \mid \exists M_d \in R(N, M_0), \nexists t \in T, M_d[t], M_0[\sigma]M_d\}$. In the following it is assumed that t_u is included in the set T , i.e., $t_u \in T$. The definition of codiagnosability in LPN systems without the deadlock-freeness assumption can be given in the following part. Here, we denote by $\psi(T_f) = \{\sigma t \in L^\omega(N, M_0) \mid \sigma \in T^*, t \in T_f\}$ the set of firing transition sequences in $L^\omega(N, M_0)$ that end with a fault transition $t \in T_f$.

Definition 3.1 (Codiagnosability): An LPN system $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$, that is monitored by a set of sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$, is codiagnosable with respect to the set of fault transitions T_f if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \sigma' \in \psi(T_f), \exists h \in \mathbb{N}, \forall \sigma'' \in L^\omega(N, M_0) / \sigma', |\sigma''| \geq h \\ \implies \exists j \in \mathcal{J}, \forall \sigma \in l_j^{-1}(l^j(\sigma' \sigma'')), \exists t_f \in T_f : t_f \in \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

\diamond

This definition implies that an LPN system is codiagnosable concerning T_f if each fault in T_f can be detected by at least one site $j \in \mathcal{J}$.

To determine the dead markings of the LPN system based on EBRG, we should first verify if each extended basis marking is dead or each marking subset, reached by firing the unobservable transitions $t \in T_{r,u}$ from an extended basis marking, contains dead markings. This verification method is similar to the one stated by proposition in [39] via replacing the T_{reg} as $T_{r,u}$. Here we denote by $R_{r,u}(M) = \{M' \mid M[\sigma_{r,u}]M', \sigma_{r,u} \in T_{r,u}^*\}$ as the set of markings obtained by firing unobservable sequences whose transitions belong to $T_{r,u}$.

Proposition 3.2 ([39]): Given an LPN system $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ and a marking M , there exists at least one dead marking in $R_{r,u}(M)$ if and only if the following linear integer constraint $D(M)$ is feasible:

$$D(M) = \begin{cases} M_d = M + C_{r,u} \cdot y \geq \mathbf{0}, \\ y \in \mathbb{N}^{T_{r,u}}, \\ \rho(M_d). \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\rho(M_d) : \bigwedge_{t \in T} (\bigvee_{p \in \bullet t} M_d(p) \leq Pre(p, t) - 1)$. \diamond

In plain words, $\rho(M_d)$ is used to denote the set of dead markings that can be described by a set of linear equalities characterizing the enabling conditions of transitions. Moreover, remark that the dead markings in $R_{r,u}(M_i)$ may not be unique. Subsequently, we present a new structure called ε -EBRG that is an augmented basis reachability graph where a self-loop labeled with $t_u(\varepsilon)$ is added to each marking M_d at which some unobservable transitions can fire such that a dead marking is reached. We denote by $\langle N', \Sigma, l', M_0 \rangle$ the nonfailure subset of $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ (or T' -induced subnet of N), where $T' = T \setminus T_f$. $L(N', M_0)$ is the transition

sequences formed with the sequences of $L(N, M_0)$ without fault transitions, and l' is equal to l restricted to $T \setminus T_f$. Then two reachability graphs are illustrated using the notion of extended basis markings.

Definition 3.3: Given an LPN system $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$, let $G_e = (X_e, E, \delta, M_0)$ be the EBRG. The ε -BRG of S is a non-deterministic finite state automaton $G_\varepsilon = (X_\varepsilon, E_\varepsilon, \delta_\varepsilon, M_0)$, where:

- $X_\varepsilon = X_e$ is the set of states.
- $E_\varepsilon \subseteq E \cup \{t_u(\varepsilon)\}$ is the event labels.
- the transition relation δ_ε is defined as follows:
 $\delta_\varepsilon = \delta \cup \{(M_i, t_u(\varepsilon), M_i) \mid D(M_i) \text{ is feasible}\}$.
- M_0 is the initial state. \diamond

A nonfailure ε -BRG with respect to site $j \in \mathcal{J}$, denoted by $G_{\varepsilon,n}^j = (X_{\varepsilon,n}^j, E_{\varepsilon,n}^j, \delta_{\varepsilon,n}^j, M_0)$, is the ε -BRG derived from $\langle N', \Sigma, l', M_0 \rangle$ following the assumption that the set of observable transitions is equal to $T_o^j \cup T_{r,a}$.

Remark 3.4: With a slight modification of q -BRG definition in [39] that introduces an observable quiescent event q to characterize the existence of deadlocks in the system, we use unobservable string ε to represent that the system may reach a dead marking without any output observation. Based on the ε -BRG structure, an attack strategy is then developed to violate the codiagnosability.

Example 1: Given an LPN system S as depicted in Fig. 1, its extended basis markings are listed in Table I. Particularly, there exists a dead marking $M_d = M_3$, where the token enters place p_7 such that no transition is enabled.

Fig. 1. LPN system $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ with a dead marking.

TABLE I
THE EXTENDED BASIS MARKING OF LPN SYSTEM IN FIG. 1.

M_0	[1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0]	0^T
M_1	[0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0]	0^T
M_2	[0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0]	0^T
M_3	[0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0]	0^T
M_4	[0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0]	0^T
M_5	[0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0]	0^T
M_6	[0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0]	0^T
M_7	[0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1]	0^T
M_8	[0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0]	1^T

Assume that the LPN system S is monitored by two sites with $\Sigma^1 = \{a, b, d\}$ and $\Sigma^2 = \{a, c, d\}$. By Definition 3.3, its ε -BRG and the nonfailure ε -BRGs are shown in Fig. 2. As depicted in Fig.2, once a dead marking M_3 is reached, we add

a self-loop encoded with an unobservable transition t_u that is labeled with ε . \diamond

Fig. 2. (a) ε -BRG of LPN system as shown in Fig. 1. (b) nonfailure ε -BRG for site 1. (c) nonfailure ε -BRG for site 2.

The unfolded verifier proposed in [29] is used for codiagnosability analysis in a decentralized framework, which is constructed by the parallel composition [40] of the EBRG and all the nonfailure EBRGs. In the following, an extended unfolded verifier applying for a more general net that contains deadlocks is defined based on the notion of the ε -BRGs.

Definition 3.5: Given an LPN system S that is monitored by a set of sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$, its ε -BRG is G_ε and the j -th nonfailure ε -BRG is $G_{\varepsilon,n}^j$. The ε -unfolded verifier (ε -UV) $U_\varepsilon = (X_\varepsilon^U, E_\varepsilon^U, \delta_\varepsilon^U, M_0^U)$ is a finite state automaton constructed by the parallel composition of the ε -BRG and all the nonfailure ε -BRGs. \diamond

For the sake of simplicity, only two local sites monitoring the LPN system are considered in the following discussion. In detail, a node $(M, \alpha; M', M'')$ in the ε -UV is called an α -state, in which α can be either N to represent the normal behavior of system without the occurrence of fault from the initial state to this one, or F to denote the occurrence of faulty behavior of system. Furthermore, in a path of U_ε , the state is tagged as “duplicate” if it already exists from the root of U_ε , and it is called a duplicate α -state. The transitions of ε -UV are tuples $(\gamma, \gamma^1, \gamma^2)$ where: (1) γ either corresponds to a transition in the ε -BRG G_ε or to ε (i.e., ε represents the empty string); (2) γ^1 (γ^2) either corresponds to a transition in the nonfailure ε -BRG $G_{\varepsilon,n}^1$ ($G_{\varepsilon,n}^2$) or to ε .

The following definition presents the notion of elementary

unsound path that leads to the violation of codiagnosability. Precisely, the existence of this type of path shows that, for each site, two arbitrarily long transition sequences of LPN system have the same observation and one of them contains the fault transition, such that the occurrence of the fault cannot be detected in a finite number of steps. Given an automaton G , we write $M \xrightarrow[G]{\sigma} M'$ to denote that M' is reached in G from M with a sequence σ .

Definition 3.6: Given an ε -unfolded verifier $U_\varepsilon = (X_\varepsilon^U, E_\varepsilon^U, \delta_\varepsilon^U, M_0^U)$, a sequence $\tilde{\sigma} = (\gamma_1, \gamma_1^1, \gamma_1^2)(\gamma_2, \gamma_2^1, \gamma_2^2) \cdots (\gamma_\theta, \gamma_\theta^1, \gamma_\theta^2)$ with $\sigma'_\alpha = \gamma_1 \cdots \gamma_q, \sigma'_\beta = \gamma_{q+1} \cdots \gamma_\theta, \sigma'_\alpha = \gamma_1^1 \cdots \gamma_q^1$, and $\sigma'_\beta = \gamma_{q+1}^1 \cdots \gamma_\theta^1$ with $j = 1, 2$, is said to be elementary unsound path if there exists $M, M^j \in X_\varepsilon$ satisfying the following conditions: 1) $M_0 \xrightarrow[G'_e]{\sigma'_\alpha} M \xrightarrow[G'_e]{\sigma'_\beta} M^j$; 2) $M_0 \xrightarrow[G'_{e,n}]{\sigma'_\alpha} M^j \xrightarrow[G'_{e,n}]{\sigma'_\beta} M$; 3) $t_f \in \sigma'_\alpha \sigma'_\beta$; 4) $l^j(\sigma'_{\alpha,k}) = l^j(\sigma'_{\alpha,k})$ and $l^j(\sigma'_{\beta,k}) = l^j(\sigma'_{\beta,k})$; 5) no prefix of $\tilde{\sigma}$ satisfies conditions (1)–(4).

Proposition 3.7: An LPN system $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ is codiagnosable if and only if there exist no elementary unsound paths in the corresponding ε -UV.

Proof: If the LPN system is deadlock-free, the proof procedure is same as the one in [29]. Once the LPN system contains the deadlock, a self-loop encoded with an unobservable transition t_u (that is not observed by system and labeled with the empty string ε) is added to each dead marking, then the net system becomes deadlock-free. ■

Example 2: The ε -UV, as displayed in Fig. 3, is constructed by the parallel composition of all the ε -BRGs. We deduce that the LPN system is codiagnosable since its site 2 with event set $\Sigma^2 = \{a, c, d\}$ is codiagnosable with respect to fault transition t_{11} . Precisely, the occurrence of fault t_{11} can be detected by observing the event label c at site 2. In other words, at this site we cannot find two arbitrarily long sequences that hold same observation, and one contains fault while the other not, i.e., there is no elementary unsound path in the ε -UV. ◇

Fig. 3. Part of the ε -UV.

B. Replacement and stealthy attack

The architecture of codiagnosability analysis under attacks is presented in Fig. 4. To investigate the codiagnosability of the LPN system, we consider the Protocol 3 in [32] that does not require any coordination between sites, i.e., each site has its own event set, such that a net is said to be codiagnosable with respect to a fault if at least one site could deduce the occurrence of the fault within finite steps. In terms of attack process for compromising the codiagnosability of LPN systems in this decentralized setting, attackers are designed to execute their corruption actions separately at each site such that no site can detect any fault in the system. Specifically, we focus on the following case: i) an attacker corrupts the system observation based on the labeling function of its located site; ii) a coordination between attackers is applied to achieve the attacker's goal. Elaborately, for any common transition that belongs to different sites, once its transition label is replaced by one attacker in a site, it has the same corrupted observation at other sites when existing.

Fig. 4. Decentralized architecture for codiagnosability under attackers.

To characterize the capability of an attacker or intruder that masks the transition labels at each site, a replacement attack structure (attack structure for short) is presented as follows. To make the exposition clear, we denote by $\Sigma_\varepsilon^j = \Sigma^j \cup \{\varepsilon\}$ the event set of site j containing empty string.

Definition 3.8 (Attack structure): Let $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ be an LPN system monitored by a set of sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$. An attack structure is defined as the set $\mathcal{A} \in 2^{((T_o \cup T_{r,a}) \times \Sigma_\varepsilon) \times ((T_o \cup T_{r,a}) \times \Sigma_\varepsilon)}$, i.e., \mathcal{A} is a set of transition pairs, each associated to its label: the first transition is associated to the original label while the second one is associated to the replaced label. For each site j and for any transition $t \in T_o^j \cup T_{r,a}$ with $l(t) = e \in \Sigma_\varepsilon^j$, the corresponding attack structure of site j is

$$\mathcal{A}^j = \begin{cases} \{(t(e), t(e')) \mid (t(e), t(e')) \in \mathcal{A}, e' \in \Sigma_\varepsilon^j\} \\ \{(t(e), t(\varepsilon)) \mid (t(e), t(e')) \in \mathcal{A}, e' \notin \Sigma_\varepsilon^j\}. \end{cases}$$

In plain words, concerning each pair $(t(e), t(e')) \in \mathcal{A}$, if the replaced transition label e' belongs to the event set Σ_ε^j of site j , then it holds the label e' in the attack structure of site j as $(t(e), t(e')) \in \mathcal{A}^j$. Otherwise, it holds the empty string ε as $(t(e), t(\varepsilon)) \in \mathcal{A}^j$ since the site j cannot observe the replaced

transition label e' , i.e., $e' \notin \Sigma_\varepsilon^j$. Remark that each transition with respect to the attack structure may be replaced with one or several different labels or empty string. For instance, an attack structure is $\mathcal{A}^j = \{(t_k(a), t_k(b)), (t_k(a), t_k(\varepsilon)), (t_i(c), t_i(d))\}$, with respect to site $j \in \mathcal{J}$, that assigns to transition t_k either a label b or ε from the original label a , and transition t_i a label d from the original label c under the corresponding attacks. For the sake of clarity, we denote by $T_{as}^j = \{t \in T_o^j \cup T_{r,a}^j \mid \exists e' \in \Sigma_\varepsilon^j, (t(e), t(e')) \in \mathcal{A}^j\}$ the set of *attackable transitions* with respect to the attack structure \mathcal{A}^j , and denote by $\Sigma_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t) = \{e' \in \Sigma_\varepsilon^j \mid (t(e), t(e')) \in \mathcal{A}^j, t \in T_{as}^j, e = l^j(t)\}$ the set of replaced labels associated with transition t while taking into account the attack structure \mathcal{A}^j .

In this work, an attack is modeled by a function that associates a transition with a unique observation, i.e., original or replaced label, which is formally defined in the following part. Particularly, at each site j , after the occurrence of a transition in T_{as}^j , it is possible to observe its original label or a replaced label, such that the given attack structure \mathcal{A}^j may cause multiple attack options.

Definition 3.9 (Replacement attack tuple): Let $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ be an LPN system that is monitored by sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$ and \mathcal{A} be an attack structure. A replacement attack tuple is denoted by $A = (A^1, A^2, \dots, A^\xi)$, where a replacement attack A^j (attack for short) is a modified labeling function that is the mapping $l_a^j : T^* \rightarrow \Sigma_\varepsilon^j$ where

$$l_a^j(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon,$$

$$l_a^j(t) = \begin{cases} l^j(t) & \text{if } t \in T \setminus T_{as}^j, \\ l^j(t) \text{ or } e' \in \Sigma_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t) & \text{if } t \in T_{as}^j, \end{cases}$$

$$l_a^j(\sigma t) = l_a^j(\sigma)l_a^j(t), \sigma \in T^*, t \in T. \quad \diamond$$

Note that each transition $t \in T_{as}^j$, under the attack A^j , is either associated with the original label $l^j(t)$ or a replaced label $e' \in \Sigma_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t)$ in term of attack structure \mathcal{A}^j .

One remark is that the considered replacement attack contains some particular insertion and removal cases. For instance, if an unobservable transition is associated to a label under the attack, it is an insertion attack; If an observable transition is associated with an empty string, this replacement could be regarded as a removal attack.

Definition 3.10 (Stealthy attack): Given an LPN system $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ that is monitored by a set of sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$ under a replacement attack tuple A , the attack tuple A is said to be stealthy if for any transition sequence σ , its corrupted observations are contained in the language of LPN system, i.e., $\forall \sigma \in L^\omega(N, M_0), \forall j \in \mathcal{J}, l_a^j(\sigma) \in \mathcal{L}(N, M_0)$. \diamond

Precisely, stealthiness requires that, for each site, the set of corrupted observations is contained in the set of observations without attacks. This guarantees that the occurrence of attacks cannot be distinguished from the system behavior.

C. K -corruption intermittent attack

Compared with continuous or permanent attacks, intermittent attacks are more practical as they consider limited attack energy and limited attack period. Here we consider a scenario that attack could last for at most a certain period of time. To do so, we assume that after a bounded number of consecutive corrupted observations under the attacks, the replaced

transition label must be recovered, which leads to a new notion of *K -corruption intermittent attack*. More precisely, in a decentralized structure, given a transition sequence $\sigma \in T^*$ and site $j \in \mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$, if the transitions $t \in T_{as}^j$ have been replaced $K^j \in \mathbb{N}$ times consecutively in σ under the attacks, then their $(K^j + 1)$ th occurrence must hold its original label. Here we define a vector $K = [K^1, \dots, K^j, \dots, K^\xi]$ where ξ is the number of sites that monitor the system. The following example is used to illustrate a scenario about K -corruption intermittent attack.

Example 3: Let us consider again the LPN system as depicted in Fig. 1 that is vulnerable to the given attack structure $\mathcal{A} = \{(t_8(\varepsilon), t_8(d)), (t_{12}(c), t_{12}(\varepsilon)), (t_{13}(a), t_{13}(\varepsilon)), (t_{13}(a), t_{13}(d)), (t_{14}(\varepsilon), t_{14}(d))\}$ and is monitored by two sites, where $\Sigma^1 = \{a, b, d\}$ and $\Sigma^2 = \{a, c, d\}$. By Definition 3.8, it holds $\mathcal{A}^1 = \{(t_8(\varepsilon), t_8(d)), (t_{13}(a), t_{13}(\varepsilon)), (t_{13}(a), t_{13}(d)), (t_{14}(\varepsilon), t_{14}(d))\}$, and $\mathcal{A}^2 = \{(t_8(\varepsilon), t_8(d)), (t_{12}(c), t_{12}(\varepsilon)), (t_{13}(a), t_{13}(\varepsilon)), (t_{13}(a), t_{13}(d)), (t_{14}(\varepsilon), t_{14}(d))\}$. In addition, we get the sets of attackable transitions with respect to \mathcal{A}^1 and \mathcal{A}^2 as $T_{as}^1 = \{t_8, t_{13}, t_{14}\}$ and $T_{as}^2 = \{t_8, t_{12}, t_{13}, t_{14}\}$, respectively. The LPN system executes a sequence $\sigma = t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{13} t_{14}$. We assume that the maximum consecutive corruption vector is $K = [1 \ 2]$ where $K^1 = 1$ and $K^2 = 2$.

For site $j = 1$ with $\Sigma^1 = \{a, b, d\}$, and it has the original observation $l^1(\sigma) = aa$ and all the possible corrupted observations are $\{a, ad, add\}$. Specifically, the unobservable transitions t_1, t_{11} and the observable transitions t_2, t_{12} cannot be attacked since $t_1, t_2, t_{11}, t_{12} \notin T_{as}^1$ and holds $l^1(t_1) = l^1(t_{11}) = l^1(t_{12}) = \varepsilon, l^1(t_2) = a$. The word “ aa ” is observed if there is no any attack; “ a ” is observed if the label of transition t_{13} is replaced by the empty string ε . In particular, the observation “ add ” is obtained if both labels of transitions t_{13} and t_{14} are replaced by d . However, the consecutive corruption $K^{1'} = 2$ exceeds the maximum one $K^1 = 1$, thus this case with the observation add cannot exist in the K -corruption intermittent attack setting but could exist in the permanent attack setting. \diamond

At each site j , to distinguish the occurrence of a transition $t \in T_{as}^j$ that is associated with its original label from the replaced one, we denote by t^a the transition t whose label is replaced under an attack, and by t^{na} the transition t that holds its original observation, respectively. Given an LPN system and a site j , under an attack A^j , let $T_a^j = \{t_i^a : t_i \in T_{as}^j \mid l_a^j(t_i) \neq l^j(t_i)\}$ be the set of attackable transitions that are associated with other labels, and let $T_{na}^j = \{t_i^{na} : t_i \in T_{as}^j \mid l_a^j(t_i) = l^j(t_i)\}$ be the set of attackable transitions that hold their original labels.

Inspired from the approach in [35], to obtain all the corrupted possibilities of a transition sequence under an attack for each site j , we define an insertion function $I_j : T^* \rightarrow 2^{(T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^*}$, where $I_j(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon, I_j(t) = \{tt^a, tt^{na}\}$, if $t \in T_{as}^j$, otherwise $I_j(t) = t$. Moreover, $I_j(\sigma t) = I_j(\sigma)I_j(t)$ for all $\sigma \in T^*$ and $t \in T$. The inverse of insert function is defined as $I_j^{-1} : (T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^* \rightarrow T^*$, where $I_j^{-1}(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon, I_j^{-1}(tt^a) = t, I_j^{-1}(tt^{na}) = t$, if $t \in T_{as}^j$, otherwise $I_j^{-1}(t) = t$. Moreover, $I_j^{-1}(\sigma t) = I_j^{-1}(\sigma)I_j^{-1}(t)$ for all $\sigma \in (T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^*$ and $t \in (T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)$. We denote by $P_{a,na}^j : (T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^* \rightarrow$

$(T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^*$ the projection over $T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j$, and denote by $P_{a,na}^{f,j} : (T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^* \rightarrow (T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j \cup T_f)^*$ the projection over $T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j \cup T_f$. In the following, we formally present K -corruption intermittent attacks in the LPN system.

Definition 3.11 (*K-corruption intermittent attack*): Let $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ be an LPN system that is monitored by a set of sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$ and is vulnerable to the attack structure \mathcal{A} . Given a transition sequence $\sigma \in T^*$ and a site j , a function that models the intermittent attack, such that the maximum number of consecutive corrupted observations is K^j , is a mapping

$$\Phi_j : T^* \rightarrow 2^{(T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^*}$$

where a sequence $\sigma^+ \in \Phi_j(\sigma)$, if σ^+ satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $\sigma^+ \in I_j(\sigma)$;
- (ii) for all $\mu', \mu'' \in (T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^*$ and $\mu''' \in T_a^{j*}$, such that $P_{a,na}^{j,j}(\sigma^+) = \mu' \mu'' \mu'''$, then $|\mu''| \leq K^j$. \diamond

Condition (i) ensures that the sequence σ^+ is obtained from the insertion function $I_j(\sigma)$. Condition (ii) guarantees that the maximum number of consecutive corrupted observations of σ is K^j in the site j .

Remark 3.12: For scenarios where attacks can only last for a limited period, such as camera downtime during security personnel shifts or maintenance periods, or due to limited attack energy, the intermittent attack model with a specified K value can be used. This K value represents the maximum number of consecutive corrupted labels allowed during an attack. If $K \rightarrow +\infty$, the attack model resembles a continuous or permanent attack, as it removes constraints on the maximum consecutive corrupted labels. Conversely, if $K = 0$, it indicates a safe environment for the systems where no transition labels can be attacked.

Remark 3.13: The work [35] touches upon the K -loss observation that could be regarded as a special case in this work, i.e., the loss observations implies that some observable transitions are replaced into empty string under attacks. However, the proposed attack model is more flexible to characterize different attack cases, for instance, the first case is the transition label could be replaced into different labels not only the empty string; the second case is that an unobservable transition associated with a candidate sensor could also be attacked, such as restarting the sensor to obtain a new observation.

Example 4: Let the LPN system S be monitored by two sites and the event sets be $\Sigma^1 = \{a, b, d\}$ and $\Sigma^2 = \{a, c, d\}$. Assume that the system executes a transition sequence $\sigma = t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{13} t_{14}$ and $K = [1 \ 2]$, according to Definition 3.11, the following sequences can be generated since K -corruption intermittent attacks.

- For site $j = 1$, it has $\Phi_1(\sigma) = \{t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{13} t_{13}^{na} t_{14} t_{14}^{na}, t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{13} t_{13}^{na} t_{14} t_{14}^{na}, t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{13} t_{13}^{na} t_{14} t_{14}^a\}$ whose projection over $(T_a^1 \cup T_{na}^1)^*$ is $P_{a,na}^1(\sigma^+) = \{t_{13}^{na} t_{14}^{na}, t_{13}^{na} t_{14}^{na}, t_{13}^{na} t_{14}^a\}$.
- For site $j = 2$, it has $\Phi_2(\sigma) = \{t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{12}^a t_{13} t_{13}^a, t_{14} t_{14}^{na}, \dots, t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{12}^{na} t_{13} t_{13}^a t_{14} t_{14}^{na}\}$ whose projection over $(T_a^2 \cup T_{na}^2)^*$ is $P_{a,na}^2(\sigma^+) = \{t_{12}^a t_{13} t_{14}^{na}, \dots, t_{12}^{na} t_{13} t_{14}^{na}\}$. \diamond

D. Problem statement

In practice, many cyber physical systems can be efficiently modeled by Petri nets or LPN, such as automated manufacturing processes [41], resource allocation systems [42], and intelligent transportation networks [43], [44]. From an attacker viewpoint, the violation of system security properties, such as opacity and diagnosability, can lead to potential damage in pursuit of the attacker's objectives. Meanwhile, the K -corruption intermittent attack is considered in this paper to address attack scenarios with constraints such as limited attack energy or limited attack periods. In the following, we formulate the addressed problem in this work.

Problem 1: Given an LPN system $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ that is monitored by a set of sites $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$ and vulnerable to an attack structure \mathcal{A} , the aim is to design the stealthy K -corruption intermittent attacks such that the codiagnosability of the system is violated.

The following assumptions hold for the codiagnosability analysis under the attacks in the LPN systems.

(A1) The LPN system is bounded.

(A2) The $(T \setminus T_o^j)$ -induced subnet is acyclic for all $j \in \mathcal{J}$.

The two assumptions are common for the diagnosability or codiagnosability analysis in the LPN systems, as the works in [20], [29], [39]. Specifically, assumption (A1) ensures that ε -BRG of the LPN system is always finite while assumption (A2) allows to use the state equation to characterize the markings that are reached by firing unobservable transitions from an extended basis marking, and guarantees that an ε -BRG contains a correct abstract representation of a net reachability set.

IV. K-CORRUPTION INTERMITTENT ATTACKS FOR VIOLATING THE CODIAGNOSABILITY

A. K-corruption Intermittent attack automaton

In this part, we present an algorithm to construct a K^j -corruption intermittent attack automaton for each site $j \in \mathcal{J}$, which models the attacked behavior considering the maximum consecutive number of K^j corrupted observations.

Algorithm 1 lists all the possible attacked sequences within K^j consecutive corrupted observations in the attack automaton, where Q^j is the set of states, $T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j$ is the set of transitions, δ^j is the transition relation, and Q_0^j is the initial state. Each state of Q^j is a tuple formed by the occurrence of attacked transition t^a (or the occurrence of each transition $t \in T_{as}^j$) and a counter with the number of corrupted observations of t , i.e., $(t^a, i) \in Q^j$ and $(t, i) \in Q^j$. More precisely, line 1 initializes the state set, the initial state, and two indexes. The initial state $Q_0^j = (t^a, 0)$ implies that the number of consecutive corrupted observations t^a is 0. In the lines 2–11, the occurrence of a transition $t \in T_{as}^j$ generates a new state (t, i) and a transition from (t^a, i) to state (t, i) , while the occurrence of a transition $t \in T \setminus T_{as}^j$ remains the state (t^a, i) and displays as a self-loop transition. If a transition t in the state (t, i) is not attacked, i.e., $t \in T_{na}^j$, the state (t, i) reaches $(t^a, 0)$. In other words, the occurrence of t^{na} resets the counter as 0. Lines 12–15 present that the occurrence of transition t^a (the label of transition t is replaced by others under the attack)

Algorithm 1: Construction of an attack automaton Δ^j for a site j

Input: $K^j, \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle, T_a^j, T_{na}^j$

Output: $\Delta^j = (Q^j, T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j, \delta^j, Q_0^j)$

1 Let $Q_0^j = (t^a, 0), Q^j = \emptyset, i = 0, q = 0;$

2 **while** $i \leq K^j$ **do**

3 $Q^j = Q^j \cup \{(t^a, i)\};$

4 **for** $t \in T$ **do**

5 **if** $t \in T_{as}^j$ **then**

6 $Q^j = Q^j \cup \{(t, i)\};$

7 $\delta^j((t^a, i), t) = (t, i);$

8 $\delta^j((t, i), t^{na}) = (t^a, 0);$

9 **if** $t \in T \setminus T_{as}^j$ **then**

10 $\delta^j((t^a, i), t) = (t^a, i);$

11 $i = i + 1;$

12 **while** $q < K^j$ **do**

13 **for** $t \in T_{as}^j$ **do**

14 $\delta^j((t, q), t^a) = (t^a, q + 1);$

15 $q = q + 1;$

increases the counter and creates the transition from state (t^a, q) to state $(t^a, q+1)$. Consequently, the maximum number of consecutive occurrences of tt^a , without the occurrence of tt^{na} , is equal to K^j .

Example 5: Consider the LPN system S in Example 3 and $K = [1 \ 2]$, by using Algorithm 1, the K -corruption intermittent attack automaton Δ^j for each site j is given as shown in Fig. 5. For the sake of simplicity, we denote by $T_{r,u}^j = T \setminus T_{as}^j$ for $j = 1, 2$. \diamond

Fig. 5. (a) Attack automaton Δ^1 with $t_i \in T_{as}^1$ and $K^1 = 1$. (b) Attack automaton Δ^2 with $t_i \in T_{as}^2$ and $K^2 = 2$.

For any site j , the LPN system under K^j -corruption intermittent attacks can be characterized by the parallel composition of the ε -BRG G_e and all the automata Δ^j or the nonfailure ε -BRG $G_{e,n}^j$ and the automaton Δ^j , such that $G'_e = G_e \parallel \Delta^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Delta^\xi$ and $G'_{e,n} = G_{e,n}^j \parallel \Delta^j$. Note that “ \parallel ” denotes the operation of parallel composition. To

make the exposition clear, in the following let us denote by $L(G_e), L(G'_e), L(G_{e,n}^j), L(G'_{e,n})$ the languages generated by the graphs $G_e, G'_e, G_{e,n}^j, G'_{e,n}$ that contain the set of firing transition sequences, respectively.

Lemma 4.1: For all transition sequences $\sigma \in L(G'_e)$ (resp., $\sigma \in L(G'_{e,n})$), it holds $I_j^{-1}(\sigma) \in L(G_e)$ (resp., $I_j^{-1}(\sigma) \in L(G_{e,n}^j)$), and that their maximum consecutive corruption is equal to or less than K^j .

Proof: Consider a sequence $\sigma \in L(G'_e)$, where G'_e is obtained by the parallel composition of G_e and all the attack automata with respect to different sites $\Delta^1, \dots, \Delta^\xi$. By using the inverse of insert function I_j^{-1} , all the transitions belonging to $T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j$ will be removed, such that it holds $I_j^{-1}(\sigma) \in L(G_e)$. Similarly, for a sequence $\sigma \in L(G'_{e,n})$, it holds $I_j^{-1}(\sigma) \in L(G_{e,n}^j)$. The part of that their maximum consecutive corruption is equal to or less than K^j for each sequence in G'_e and $G'_{e,n}$ is similar to the proof in [35] without the consideration of the communication channel. \blacksquare

Example 6: Continue the Example 3, the partial parts of $G'_e = G_e \parallel \Delta^1 \parallel \Delta^2$ and $G'_{e,n} = G_{e,n}^j \parallel \Delta^j$ for site $j=1, 2$, are generated as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. In detail, the state of G'_e and $G'_{e,n}$ is a tuple formed by the extended basis marking and its corresponding state of attack automaton. \diamond

B. Complete attack graph

In this part, we present an approach for the construction of a complete attack graph that generates all the potential paths to be attacked, possibly leading to an elementary unsound path that violates the codiagnosability in the system, which is shown in the following algorithm.

Algorithm 2 outputs a complete attack graph $U_c = (X_c^u, E_c^u, \delta_c^u, x_0^u)$, where X_c^u is the set of states, E_c^u is the event set, δ_c^u is the transition relation, and x_0^u is the initial state. In contrast to the classic verifier approaches in [29], [31] that are obtained by using the parallel composition of failure graph and nonfailure graphs, a state of the proposed complete attack graph is updated even though for a transition (t, t_1, t_2) , it holds $l(t) \neq l^1(t_1)$ and $l(t) \neq l^2(t_2)$. In addition, such a complete attack graph integrates the proposed attack automaton, such that all the potential attacked paths limited to K consecutive corruptions are listed. Given the attack structure with respect to each site, it is possible either to associate transition t with a label $e \in \Sigma$ or to replace the label of transition t as empty string ε . Then the observation of transitions in the tuple (t, t_1, t_2) becomes same or the transition sequence in the consecutive tuples has the same observation, such that the path containing (t, t_1, t_2) is possible to be attacked into an elementary unsound path.

Precisely, line 1 initializes the state set, the initial state and four indices q, k, β, γ . The initial state $x_0^u = [M_0, (t^a, 0), (t^a, 0), N; M_0^1, (t^a, 0); M_0^2, (t^a, 0)]$ implies that there is no fault at initial state with N symbol and the number of consecutive corrupted observations t^a is 0 with $(t^a, 0)$. Lines 2–23, at each untagged state, iteratively generate all the other states by enumerating the consecutive transition pairs whatever the observation of transitions in the pair is same or not. In details, lines 4–18 consider all the possibilities of

Fig. 6. Parallel composition of ε -BRG and K -corruption attack automata Δ^1 and Δ^2 .

Fig. 7. (a) Parallel composition of nonfailure ε -BRG $G_{e,n}^1$ and K^1 -corruption attack automaton Δ^1 . (b) Parallel composition of nonfailure ε -BRG $G_{e,n}^2$ and K^2 -corruption attack automaton Δ^2 .

transitions t, t_1, t_2 to update all the attacked paths. Meanwhile, lines 21–22 recall the Algorithm 1 to update the counter of consecutive corrupted observations for each state, such that each updated state verifies the K -corruption intermittent attack setting, i.e., at each site j , the maximum consecutive corruption of a transition sequence cannot exceed its corresponding K^j .

Remark 4.2. By relaxing the restriction $l(t) = l^1(t_1)$ and $l(t) = l^2(t_2)$ for each transition (t, t_1, t_2) , the proposed approach explores all the attacked paths, thereby gaining potential benefits by analyzing possible attacks and better designing a robust system against attacks (if necessary). However, the complexity analysis will be high due to such a search approach. To reduce the complexity effort, it is possible to establish a balance between the partial search of state space and attack possibilities in future work.

C. Potential attacked path

The basic idea of this paper is, from the viewpoint of attackers, to replace transition labels by taking into account K -corruption intermittent attack setting, such that a path in the complete attack graph U_c becomes an elementary unsound path that violates the codiagnosability. By applying Algorithm 2, we could list all the paths in the graph. However, to reduce the complexity effort, we only find out all the paths that are possible to be attacked into elementary unsound paths, which are called potential attacked paths. In order to define the potential attacked paths, we present some necessary notions here for clarity. Given a transition sequence σ and $t \in \sigma$, here we denote the projection $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j : (T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^* \rightarrow (T \cup T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j)^*$, such that

$$\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(t) = \begin{cases} t, & \forall t \in T_a^j \cup T_{na}^j \cup (T_o^j \setminus T_{as}^j), \\ \varepsilon, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Algorithm 2: Construction of a complete attack graph for finding all the attack paths

Input: EBRGs $G'_e, G^{1'}$ and $G^{2'}$
Output: $U_c = (X_c^u, E_c^u, \delta_c^u, x_0^u)$

```

1 Let  $k = q = \beta = \gamma = 0, X_c^u = \{x_0^u\}, E_c^u = \emptyset, \delta_c^u = \emptyset,$ 
 $x_0^u = [M_0, (t^a, 0), (t^a, 0), N; M_0^1, (t^a, 0); M_0^2, (t^a, 0)]$ 
be the initial state;
2 while states with no tag exist do
3   select a state  $x_1^u = [M_1, (t, q), (t, k), \alpha; M_2^1, (t, \beta);$ 
 $M_2^2, (t, \gamma)]$  with no tag;
4   for  $\forall t \in T_o \cup T_f \cup T_{r,a}, \forall t_1 \in T_o^1 \cup T_{r,a},$  and
 $\forall t_2 \in T_o^2 \cup T_{r,a}$  do
5     if  $t \in T_o^1 \cap T_o^2, (M_1, t, M_1') \in \delta,$ 
 $(M_2^1, t_1, M_2^1') \in \delta^1, (M_2^2, t_2, M_2^2') \in \delta^2,$  then
6        $X_c^u = X_c^u \cup \{x_2^u = [M_1', (t, q), (t, k), \alpha;$ 
 $M_2^1', (t, \beta); M_2^2', (t, \gamma)]\}, E_c^u = E_c^u \cup \{(t,$ 
 $t_1, t_2)\}, \delta_c^u = \delta_c^u \cup \{x_1^u, (t, t_1, t_2), M_{i'}^u\}$ 
7     if  $t \in T_f,$  and  $(M_1, t, M_1') \in \delta$  then
8        $X_c^u = X_c^u \cup \{x_2^u = [M_1', (t, q), (t, k), F;$ 
 $M_2^1, (t, \beta); M_2^2, (t, \gamma)]\}, E_c^u = E_c^u \cup \{(t, \varepsilon,$ 
 $\varepsilon)\}, \delta_c^u = \delta_c^u \cup \{x_1^u, (t, \varepsilon, \varepsilon), M_{i'}^u\}$ 
9     if  $t \in T_o^1 \setminus T_o^2, (M_1, t, M_1') \in \delta,$ 
 $(M_2^1, t_1, M_2^1') \in \delta^1$  then
10       $X_c^u = X_c^u \cup \{x_2^u = [M_1', (t, q), (t, k), \alpha;$ 
 $M_2^1', (t, \beta); M_2^2, (t, \gamma)]\}, E_c^u = E_c^u \cup \{(t,$ 
 $t_1, \varepsilon)\}, \delta_c^u = \delta_c^u \cup \{x_1^u, (t, t_1, \varepsilon), M_{i'}^u\}$ 
11     if  $t \in T_o^2 \setminus T_o^1, (M_1, t, M_1') \in \delta,$ 
 $(M_2^2, t_1, M_2^2') \in \delta^2$  then
12       $X_c^u = X_c^u \cup \{x_2^u = [M_1', (t, q), (t, k), \alpha;$ 
 $M_2^1, (t, \beta); M_2^2', (t, \gamma)]\}, E_c^u = E_c^u \cup \{(t,$ 
 $\varepsilon, t_2)\}, \delta_c^u = \delta_c^u \cup \{x_1^u, (t, \varepsilon, t_2), M_{i'}^u\}$ 
13     if  $t \in T_{r,a},$  and  $(M_1, t, M_1') \in \delta$  then
14       $X_c^u = X_c^u \cup \{x_2^u = [M_1', (t, q), (t, k), \alpha;$ 
 $M_2^1, (t, \beta); M_2^2, (t, \gamma)]\}, E_c^u = E_c^u \cup \{(t, \varepsilon,$ 
 $\varepsilon)\}, \delta_c^u = \delta_c^u \cup \{x_1^u, (t, \varepsilon, \varepsilon), M_{i'}^u\}$ 
15     if  $t_1 \in T_{r,a},$  and  $(M_2^1, t_1, M_2^1') \in \delta^1$  then
16       $X_c^u = X_c^u \cup \{x_2^u = [M_1, (t, q), (t, k), \alpha;$ 
 $M_2^1', (t, \beta); M_2^2, (t, \gamma)]\}, E_c^u = E_c^u \cup \{(\varepsilon,$ 
 $t_1, \varepsilon)\}, \delta_c^u = \delta_c^u \cup \{x_1^u, (\varepsilon, t_1, \varepsilon), M_{i'}^u\}$ 
17     if  $t_2 \in T_{r,a},$  and  $(M_2^2, t_1, M_2^2') \in \delta^1$  then
18       $X_c^u = X_c^u \cup \{x_2^u = [M_1, (t, q), (t, k), \alpha;$ 
 $M_2^1, (t, \beta); M_2^2', (t, \gamma)]\}, E_c^u = E_c^u \cup \{(\varepsilon,$ 
 $\varepsilon, \varepsilon)\}, \delta_c^u = \delta_c^u \cup \{x_1^u, (\varepsilon, \varepsilon, t_2), M_{i'}^u\}$ 
19   if  $x_1^u$  is same as a state in the path from the initial
state then
20     tag it "duplicate";
21   for  $\forall t, t_1, t_2 \in T_a \cup T_{na}$  do
22     update the state  $[M_1', (t, q'), (t, k'), \alpha; M_2^1',$ 
 $(t_1, \beta'); M_2^2', (t_2, \gamma')]$  by Algorithm 1;
23   tag the state  $x_1^u$  "old".

```

Similarly, we denote the projection $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f : (T \cup T_a \cup T_{na})^* \rightarrow (T \cup T_a \cup T_{na})^*$, such that

$$\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f(t) = \begin{cases} t, & \forall t \in T_a \cup T_{na} \cup (T_o \setminus T_{as}) \cup T_f, \\ \varepsilon, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The projection can be extended to a transition sequence $\sigma = t_1 t_2 \dots t_i$ such that $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma) = \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(t_1) \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(t_2) \dots \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(t_i)$. For instance in Example 4, given a sequence $\sigma = t_1 t_2 t_{11} t_{12} t_{13} t_{13}^{na} t_{14} t_{14}^{na}$, for site $j = 1$ it holds $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^1(\sigma) = t_2 t_{13}^{na} t_{14}^{na}$. In detail, t_2 remains in the sequence due to $t_2 \in T_o^1 \setminus T_{as}^1$ while t_{11}, t_{12}, t_{13} and t_{14} are projected into empty string because they do not belong to the set $T_a^1 \cup T_{na}^1 \cup (T_o^1 \setminus T_{as}^1)$, i.e., $t_{11} \in T_f, t_{12} \in T_o^2, t_{13} \in T_{as}^1, t_{14} \in T_{r,a}$. Then, in order to determine if two sequences could generate same observation under the attacks, a set of possible observations of each transition and sequence is defined as follows.

Definition 4.3: Given an LPN system $\langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ and a site j , an attack structure \mathcal{A}^j and a transition t , we denote by $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t) = \{e \mid l^j(t) = e\} \cup \{e' \mid e' \in \Sigma_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t)\}$. \diamond

In plain words, $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t)$ is the set of all possible observations when transition t fires. Moreover, it holds that $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t\sigma) = l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(t)l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(\sigma), t \in T, \sigma \in T^*$.

Definition 4.4 (Potential attacked path): Given a complete attack graph $U_c = (X_c^u, E_c^u, \delta_c^u, x_0^u)$ and a set of extended basis markings X_ε , a sequence $\tilde{\sigma} = (\gamma_1, \gamma_1^+, \gamma_1^2)(\gamma_2, \gamma_2^+, \gamma_2^2) \dots (\gamma_\theta, \gamma_\theta^+, \gamma_\theta^2)$ with $\sigma_\alpha^+ = \gamma_1 \dots \gamma_\theta, \sigma_\beta^+ = \gamma_{q+1} \dots \gamma_\theta,$ $\sigma_\alpha^{j,+} = \gamma_1^j \dots \gamma_q^j,$ and $\sigma_\beta^{j,+} = \gamma_{q+1}^j \dots \gamma_\theta^j$ with $j = 1, 2$, is a potential attacked path if there exists $M, M^j \in X_\varepsilon$ satisfying the following conditions:

- C1) $M_0 \xrightarrow[G'_e]{\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f(\sigma_\alpha^+)} M \xrightarrow[G'_e]{\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f(\sigma_\beta^+)} M^j$;
- C2) $M_0 \xrightarrow[G'_{e,n}]{\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma_\alpha^{j,+})} M^j \xrightarrow[G'_{e,n}]{\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma_\beta^{j,+})} M^j, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}$;
- C3) $t_f \in \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f(\sigma_\alpha^+ \sigma_\beta^+)$;
- C4) no prefix of $\tilde{\sigma}$ satisfies items (C1)–(C3).
- C5) $\exists t \in \bigcup_{j \in \mathcal{J}} T_{as}^j$ such that $t \in \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f(\sigma_\alpha^+ \sigma_\beta^+)$ or $t \in \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma_\alpha^{j,+} \sigma_\beta^{j,+})$.

In plain words, conditions (C1)–(C4) guarantee that there exist two sequences corresponding to the chosen path $\tilde{\sigma}$ at each site j , in which one sequence contains a fault transition and the other not. In addition, the two corresponding transition sequences could be arbitrarily long after the occurrence of a fault. Considering the characteristic of elementary unsound path, the chosen path could be potentially attacked into an elementary unsound path if condition (C5) holds, i.e., there exists a transition that can be attacked. Specifically, under an attack tuple $A_i = (A_i^1, A_i^2)$ with respect to the attack structures \mathcal{A}^1 and \mathcal{A}^2 for each site, there may exist two sequences with the same observation. Assume that $\sigma_\alpha^+ \sigma_\beta^+ = \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^f(\sigma_\alpha^+ \sigma_\beta^+)$ and $\sigma_\alpha^j \sigma_\beta^j = \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma_\alpha^{j,+} \sigma_\beta^{j,+})$, by the attack structure, there may exist two observations $\omega_j \in l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(\sigma_\alpha^+ \sigma_\beta^+)$, and $\omega_j' \in l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(\sigma_\alpha^j \sigma_\beta^j)$, such that they hold the same observation $\omega_j = \omega_j'$.

Lemma 4.5: Given an LPN system S , a complete attack graph $U_c = (X_c^u, E_c^u, \delta_c^u, x_0^u)$ and the attack structure \mathcal{A} , if there are no potential attacked paths in the complete attack graph U_c , the codiagnosability of system S holds under the given attack structure \mathcal{A} .

Proof: It is obviously obtained from Definition 4.4. No potential attacked paths imply that the elementary unsound path resulting in the violation of codiagnosability cannot be generated under attacks. ■

Example 7: Given graphs G'_e and $G_{e,n}^{j'}$ with $j = 1, 2$, as shown in Figs. 6 and 7, the complete attack graph is constructed by applying Algorithm 2. Following conditions (C1)–(C5) in Definition 4.4, one potential attacked path is: $\tilde{\sigma} = (t_2, t_2, t_2)(t_{11}, \varepsilon, \varepsilon)(t_{12}, t_7, t_7)(t_{12}^a, t_7, t_7)(t_{13}, t_u, t_u)(t_{13}^a, t_u, t_u)(t_{14}, t_u, t_u)(t_{14}^a, t_u, t_u)$. It holds that the sequence $\sigma'_\alpha \sigma'_\beta = t_2 t_{11} t_{12}^a t_{13}^a t_{14}^a$ contains a fault transition t_{11} , and two sequences $\sigma_\alpha^1 \sigma_\beta^1 = \sigma_\alpha^2 \sigma_\beta^2 = t_2 t_7$ do not contain the fault transition. In addition, there exist transitions t_{12}, t_{13} that can be attacked. ◇

D. Attacks for violating the codiagnosability

Algorithm 3 computes K -corruption intermittent attacks for violating the codiagnosability in the LPN systems.

Algorithm 3: Computation of K -corruption attacks

Input: complete attack graph $U_c = (X_c^u, E_c^u, \delta_c^u, x_0^u)$, $\mathcal{J} = \{1, 2, \dots, \xi\}$ and attack structure \mathcal{A} .

Output: Attack tuple $A = \{(A^1, A^2, \dots, A^\xi)\}$.

```

1 Initialize  $k = 1, i = 1, A = \emptyset$ ;
2 Get the attack structure  $\mathcal{A}^j$  for each site  $j$  with respect
  to  $\mathcal{A}$  (see Definition 3.8);
3 Obtain all the potential attacked paths  $\Pi = \{\tilde{\sigma}_1, \tilde{\sigma}_2, \dots, \tilde{\sigma}_n\}$ 
  according to (C1)–(C5) (see Definition 4.4);
4 if  $\Pi = \emptyset$  then
5   Return “no solution”;
6 else
7   for all  $\tilde{\sigma}_k \in \Pi$  do
8      $\tilde{\sigma}_k = (\sigma_k^{1,+}, \sigma_k^{1,+}, \dots, \sigma_k^{\xi,+})$ ,  $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}$ ,
9      $\sigma_k^j = \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma_k^{j,+})$ ,  $\sigma_k^j = \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma_k^{j,+})$ ,
10     $\sigma_k^j = \sigma'_{\alpha,k} \sigma'_{\beta,k}$ ,  $\sigma_k^j = \sigma'_{\alpha,k} \sigma'_{\beta,k}$ ;
11    Compute the set  $S_{c,k}^{\alpha,j} = \{\omega_\alpha^j \in \Sigma^* \mid \omega_\alpha^j \in$ 
12     $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(\sigma_{\alpha,k}^j) \cap l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(\sigma'_{\alpha,k})\}$ ,
13     $S_{c,k}^{\beta,j} = \{\omega_\beta^j \in \Sigma^* \mid \omega_\beta^j \in l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(\sigma_{\beta,k}^j) \cap$ 
14     $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}(\sigma'_{\beta,k})\}$ ;
15    for all  $j \in \mathcal{J}$ ,  $\omega_\alpha^j \in S_{c,k}^{\alpha,j}$  and  $\omega_\beta^j \in S_{c,k}^{\beta,j}$  do
16      if  $\forall t \in T_\alpha^j \cap T_\beta^j \cup T_{r,a}$ ,  $\forall q \neq j \in \mathcal{J}$  then
17         $l_{\mathcal{A}^q}^j(t) = l_{\mathcal{A}^q}^q(t)$ ,  $l_{\mathcal{A}^q}^j(t) \in l_{\mathcal{A}^q}(t)$ ,  $l_{\mathcal{A}^q}^j(t) \in$ 
18         $l_{\mathcal{A}^q}(t)$ ;
19      if  $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}$ ,  $\forall \sigma \in L^\omega(N, M_0)$ ,  $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}^j(\sigma) \in$ 
20       $\mathcal{L}(N, M_0)$  then
21         $A = A \cup (A_i^1, A_i^2, \dots, A_i^\xi)$ ;
22         $i = i + 1$ ;
23       $k = k + 1$ ;
24   Return  $A$ ;
```

The first step initializes the indices i, k , and attacks A . Line 2 gets the attack structure \mathcal{A}^j for each site j with respect to \mathcal{A} , and then we obtain all the potential attacked paths

in the constructed U_c by verifying conditions (C1)–(C5). If there exists no potential path, i.e., $\Pi = \emptyset$, then the algorithm returns no solution implying that not any attack applying on the system could generate an elementary unsound path. The main part (lines 7–17) analyzes each potential attacked path until all the paths have been considered. More precisely, for each potential attacked path $\tilde{\sigma}_k$, we obtain sequences $\sigma_k^j = \sigma_{\alpha,k}^j \sigma_{\beta,k}^j$ and $\sigma_k^j = \sigma'_{\alpha,k} \sigma'_{\beta,k}$ by the projection $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j$ and $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j$. Line 9 gets the set of common observations for the transition sequences $\sigma_{\alpha,k}^j$ and $\sigma'_{\alpha,k}$ (resp., $\sigma_{\beta,k}^j$ and $\sigma'_{\beta,k}$). The part (lines 10–15) verifies if the common attacked transition between different sites keeps the same replaced label, and guarantees the stealthiness of attacks. In fact, the verification of stealthiness of attacks could be achieved by using the diagnoser-based approaches in [16], [20]. If verified, we store the attack tuple into attack set A . Until all the potential attacked paths are analyzed, we obtain all the attacks A .

Proposition 4.6: Given an LPN system $S = \langle N, \Sigma, l, M_0 \rangle$ satisfying Assumptions (A1)–(A2) that is vulnerable to an attack structure \mathcal{A} , Algorithm 3 computes the K -corruption intermittent attacks for violating the codiagnosability.

Proof: First, the given complete attack graph satisfies the K -corruption setting. Then, by verifying conditions (C1)–(C5), all the potential attacked paths in U_c could be obtained. By Algorithm 3, for each potential attacked path, it guarantees that sequences $\sigma_k^j = \sigma'_{\alpha,k} \sigma'_{\beta,k}$ and $\sigma_k^j = \sigma_{\alpha,k}^j \sigma_{\beta,k}^j$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}$ generate the same observation under the attacks with respect to each attack structure \mathcal{A}^j , i.e., $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}^j(\sigma_{\alpha,k}^j) = l_{\mathcal{A}^j}^j(\sigma'_{\alpha,k})$ and $l_{\mathcal{A}^j}^j(\sigma_{\beta,k}^j) = l_{\mathcal{A}^j}^j(\sigma'_{\beta,k})$, which satisfies the characteristic of elementary unsound path that violates the codiagnosability. For each common transition that belongs to different sites, it holds the same corrupted observation. In addition, the stealthiness ensures that the occurrence of attacks cannot be distinguished from the system behavior. ■

Remark 4.7: To apply the proposed method for the case of multiple r fault classes T_f^i , with $i = 1, \dots, r$, a complete attack graph $U_{c,i}$ is constructed for each fault class T_f^i . Note that in $U_{c,i}$ all fault transitions in $T_f \setminus T_f^i$ should be considered as regular unobservable transitions that cannot be attacked. Then one can compute all the potential attacked paths of $U_{c,i}$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$, and obtain the attack strategy by using Algorithm 3.

Example 8: Let us consider Example 7 again. One potential attacked path is $\tilde{\sigma} = (t_2, t_2, t_2)(t_{11}, \varepsilon, \varepsilon)(t_{12}, t_7, t_7)(t_{12}^a, t_7, t_7)(t_{13}, t_u, t_u)(t_{13}^a, t_u, t_u)(t_{14}, t_u, t_u)(t_{14}^a, t_u, t_u)$ with $\tilde{\sigma}_1 = (\sigma^{1,+}, \sigma^{1,+}, \sigma^{2,+})$, $\sigma^{1,+} = t_2 t_{11} t_{12}^a t_{13}^a t_{14}^a$, $\sigma^{1,+} = t_2 t_7 t_7^a t_u t_u$ and $\sigma^{2,+} = t_2 t_7 t_7^a t_u t_u$. Algorithm 3 first obtains the projection of three sequences $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^j(\sigma^{1,+}) = t_2 t_{11} t_{12}^a t_{13}^a t_{14}^a$ with $\sigma'_{\alpha,1} = t_2 t_{11} t_{12}^a$ and $\sigma'_{\beta,1} = t_{13}^a t_{14}^a$, $\mathcal{P}_{a,na}^1(\sigma^{1,+}) = \mathcal{P}_{a,na}^2(\sigma^{2,+}) = t_2 t_7 = \sigma_{\alpha,1}^1 = \sigma_{\beta,1}^2$, and then computes the set of common corrupted observations $S_{c,k}^{\alpha,1} = S_{c,k}^{\alpha,2} = ad$ and $S_{c,k}^{\beta,1} = S_{c,k}^{\beta,2} = \varepsilon$. The attack tuple $A = (A^1, A^2)$ that causes the common corrupted observation $(ad)\varepsilon^* = ad$, is stealthy since all the observations corresponding this attack tuple are included in $\mathcal{L}(N, M_0)$. Meanwhile, this attack tuple hides the occurrence of the fault transition t_{11} in all sites of the system, such that it leads to the violation of the codiagnosability. ◇

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work computes K -corruption intermittent attacks for violating the codiagnosability in the LPN systems. We assume that the set of observable transitions and a subset of regular unobservable transitions can be attacked or replaced with different labels with the K -corruption attack setting. Three algorithms have been proposed to obtain such attacks. Precisely, the first one is inferred to build an attack automaton that models the attacked behavior considering the maximum consecutive number of corrupted observations while the second constructs a complete attack graph to list all the potential attacked paths. Finally, the third one by analyzing all the potential attacked paths and their possible corrupted observations, returns the attacks. The coordination between attackers for each site is mainly based on the same corrupted observation for the common attacked transitions. Although the complexity is still high, the proposed decentralized approach reduces the complexity effort, which could be used for the attack strategy design for the large systems. Our future work will focus on reducing the complexity analysis of such attack model, and considering the optimization of this attack strategy. Additionally, the attack synthesis problem will be extended into unbounded systems by constructing corresponding coverability graphs.

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Maria Pia Fanti (Fellow, IEEE) received the Laurea degree in electronic engineering from the University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy, in 1983. She was a visiting researcher at the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute of Troy, New York, in 1999. Since 1983, she has been with the Department of Electrical and Information Engineering of the Polytechnic of Bari, Italy, where she is currently a Full Professor of system and control engineering and Chair of the Laboratory of Automation and Control. Her research interests include management and modeling of complex systems, such as intelligent transportation, logistics and manufacturing systems; discrete event systems; Petri nets; consensus protocols; fault detection. Prof. Fanti has published more than 350 papers and two textbooks on her research topics.

She is senior editor of the IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering, and Associate Editor of the IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems and of the IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles. She was member of the Board of Governors of the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society, and of the Administrative Committee of the IEEE Robotics and Automaton Society, founder and chair of the Technical Committee on Automation in Logistics of the IEEE Robotics and Automation Society. Prof. Fanti was general chair, program chair and member of the organizing committee of a large number of international conference in particular she was General Chair of the 2011 IEEE Conference on Automation Science and Engineering, the 2017 IEEE International Conference on Service Operations and Logistics, and Informatics and the 2019 IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Conference.

Ruotian Liu (Member, IEEE) received the B.S. degree in automation from Xidian University, Xi'an, China, in 2015, and M.S. and the Ph.D. degrees in automation from Aix-Marseille University, Marseille, France, in 2018 and 2021, respectively. In 2022, he joined Polytechnic University of Bari, Italy, where he is currently an Assistant Professor with the Department of Electrical and Information Engineering. His research interests include control theory in discrete event systems and hybrid systems, diagnosability/opacity analysis, networked security.

Yihui Hu received the B.S. degree in electrical engineering and automation from Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology, Xi'an, China, in 2016, the First Ph.D. degree in control theory and control engineering from Xidian University, Xi'an, in 2021, and the Second Ph.D. degree in electronic and computer engineering from the University of Cagliari, Cagliari, Italy, in 2021. He is currently an Associate Professor with the School of Automation, Xi'an University of Posts and Telecommunications, Xi'an. His current research interests include discrete

event systems, automata, Petri nets, fault diagnosis, and supervisory control theory.

Agostino Marcello Mangini (Senior Member, IEEE) received the Laurea degree in electronics engineering and the Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering from the Polytechnic University of Bari, Bari, Italy, in 2003 and 2008, respectively. He has been a Visiting Scholar with the University of Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain. He is currently an Associate Professor with the Department of Electrical and Information Engineering, Polytechnic University of Bari. He has authored or coauthored over 140 printed publications. His current research interests include

modeling, simulation, control of discrete-event systems, Petri nets, deep reinforcement learning, supply chains and urban traffic networks, distribution, and internal logistics. He was on the program committees of the 2007–2023 IEEE International SMC Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics. He was on the Editorial Board of the 2017–2023 IEEE Conference on Automation Science and Engineering. Moreover, he was the Publication Chair of the 2017 IEEE SOLI and the 2019 IEEE SMC conferences, the Workshop Co-Chair of the 2023 IEEE SMC conference, the Workshop and Tutorial Chair of the 2023 IEEE CASE Conference, and the Special Session Chair of the 3rd IEEE International Conference on Automation in Manufacturing, Transportation and Logistics (iCaMaL2023). He is an Associate Editor of IEEE Transactions on Automation and Science and Engineering and IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Magazine.